

EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

EMI UI SRC v. 3.0.0

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EMI UI Service Reference Card

Daemons running

Init scripts and options (start|stop|restart|...)

Configuration files location with example or template

- /etc/profile.d/grid-env.sh
- /etc/profile.d/grid-env.csh
- /etc/arc/client.conf
- /etc/vomses
- /etc/glite-ce-common-java/
- /etc/glite-wms/
- /etc/glite_wmsui_cmd_err.conf
- /etc/glite_wmsui_cmd_help.conf
- /etc/glite_wmsui_cmd_var.conf
- /etc/unicore/

Logfile locations (and management) and other useful audit information

- /var/log

Open ports

- gLite port table -
http://jra1mw.cvs.cern.ch/cgi-bin/jra1mw.cgi/org.glite.site-info.ports/doc/?only_with_tag=HEAD

Possible unit test of the service

Where is service state held (and can it be rebuilt)

Cron jobs

- fetch-crl

Security information

Access control Mechanism description (authentication & authorization)

- The user must have an account in the host machine.

How to block/ban a user

- Delete or deactivate the user account.
- Search for files and processes created by this user activity (find, ps, lsof, ...). Then put them out from the system.

Network Usage

- Here you can find informations on glite related network connections:
http://jra1mw.cvs.cern.ch/cgi-bin/jra1mw.cgi/org.glite.site-info.ports/doc/?only_with_tag=HEAD

Firewall configuration

Security recommendations

It's recommended to use strong authentication method based on user grid certificate Be ware on file access right. It's recommended to set the system umask to 037 (all right to user, write for group none for others).

Security incompatibilities

List of externals packages that are not maintained by the supported OS.

Other security relevant comments

-- DoinaCristinaAiftimiei - 24-Apr-2011

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